

Ultrasonic investigations in ternary liquid mixtures of substituted benzenes with acetophenone at different temperatures

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Manuscript received 29 January 2009, revised 17 August 2009, accepted 21 August 2009

Abstract : The ultrasonic velocity, density and viscosity have been measured for the ternary mixtures of substituted benzenes such as chlorobenzene, bromobenzene and nitrobenzene with acetophenone in 1-butanol at 303, 308 and 313 K. The experimental data have been used to calculate the acoustical parameters namely adiabatic compressibility (β), free length (L_f), free volume (V_f), internal pressure (π_i), acoustic impedance (Z) and molar volume (V_m). Some of the above excess parameters have been evaluated and fitted to Redlich-Kister polynomials. It is eventually observed that molecular association between acetophenone and 1-butanol is through hydrogen bonding and substituted benzenes through strong dipole-dipole interactions. The formation of donor-acceptor complexes also observed in the present study.

Keywords : Adiabatic compressibility, dipole-dipole interaction, hydrogen bonding.

Introduction

In recent years, the measurement of ultrasonic velocity has been adequately employed in understanding the nature of molecular interactions in pure liquids and liquid mixtures. The ultrasonic investigations are highly sensitive to molecular interactions and can be used to provide qualitative information about the physical nature and strength of molecular interactions in the liquid mixtures¹⁻³. Ultrasonic velocity of a liquid is fundamentally related to the binding forces between the atoms or the molecules and has been adequately employed in understanding the nature of molecular interactions in pure liquids⁴⁻⁸. The variation of ultrasonic velocity and related parameters throw much light upon the structural changes associated with the liquid mixtures having weakly interacting components⁹ as well as strongly interacting components.

In the present case, the substituted benzenes taken up for study are chlorobenzene, bromobenzene and nitrobenzene. Nitrobenzene has higher dielectric constant ($\epsilon = 34.8$) value than those of chlorobenzene ($\epsilon = 5.6$) and bromobenzene ($\epsilon = 5.4$). Nitrobenzene¹⁰ is supposed to be a relatively complex molecule and its non-ideality in all probability may be due to the polarity arisen out of nitro-group which rotates freely along the C-N axis where it likely to give more flexibility to the interactions arising

due to the two highly polar N \rightarrow O bonds. Chlorine atom in chlorobenzene is an electron-withdrawing atom, tends to attract to π -electrons of the benzene ring, thereby decreases the electron density of ring. As a result, the benzene ring in chlorobenzene becomes relatively poor electron-donor towards the electron-seeking proton of any groups. Chlorobenzene is neither acidic nor basic colourless liquid with a pleasant smell. Chlorobenzene is insoluble in water and soluble in alcohol, benzene and ether. Chlorobenzene is more reactive because the chlorine atom is bonded with sp^3 hybridized carbon atom. So, the rate of reaction with chlorobenzene is faster. Bromobenzene is less reactive because of its double bond character between carbon and bromine atom. Thus, the molecular interactions is likely to be more affected resulting in a greater degree of variation with respect to the ultrasonic related parameters.

In view of the importance mentioned, an attempt has been made to elucidate the molecular interactions in the ternary liquid mixtures of substituted benzenes with acetophenone in 1-butanol at different temperatures.

Materials and methods :

The chemicals used in the present work were analytical reagent (AR) and spectroscopic reagent (SR) grade

with minimum assay of 99.9% were obtained from Sd fine chemicals, India and E. Merck, Germany and used as such without further purification. In all systems, the mole fraction of the second component, 1-butanol ($X_2 = 0.4$) was kept fixed while the mole fractions of the remaining two were varied from 0.0 to 0.6 so as to have the mixtures of different compositions. There is nothing significant in fixing the second component at the $X_2 = 0.4$. The ultrasonic velocity (U) in liquid mixtures have been measured using an ultrasonic interferometer (Mittal Enterprises, New Delhi, Model : F81) working at frequency 3 MHz with an overall accuracy of $\pm 3 \text{ ms}^{-1}$. The density (ρ) and viscosity (η) of liquids and liquid mixtures were measured using a pycnometer and an Ostwald's viscometer with an accuracy of $\pm 0.1 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$ and $\pm 0.001 \text{ Nsm}^{-2}$ respectively. All the precautions were taken to minimise the possible experimental error.

Acoustic parameters :

Using the measured data, the following acoustical parameters have been calculated.

The adiabatic compressibility (β)

$$\beta = \frac{1}{U^2 \rho} \quad (1)$$

The intermolecular free length (L_f)

$$L_f = K_T \sqrt{\beta} \quad (2)$$

where K_T is a temperature dependent constant.

Temp. (K)	303	308	313
K_T values	199.53	201.1209	203.0182
in S.I. unit	$\times 10^{-8}$	$\times 10^{-8}$	$\times 10^{-8}$

The free volume (V_f)

$$V_f = \left(\frac{M_{\text{eff}} U}{K \eta} \right)^{3/2} \quad (3)$$

where M_{eff} is the effective molecular weight ($M_{\text{eff}} = \sum m_i x_i$ in which m_i and x_i are the molecular weight and the mole fraction of the individual liquids respectively). K is a temperature independent constant which is equal to 4.28×10^9 for all liquids.

The internal pressure (π_i)

$$\pi_i = bRT \left(\frac{K\eta}{U} \right)^{1/2} \left(\frac{\rho^{2/3}}{M_{\text{eff}}^{7/6}} \right) \quad (4)$$

K is a constant, T the absolute temperature, and M_{eff} the effective molecular weight.

The acoustic impedance (Z)

$$Z = U\rho \quad (5)$$

Excess parameter (A^E) has been calculated by using the relation,

$$A^E = A_{\text{exp}} - A_{\text{id}} \quad (6)$$

where $A_{\text{id}} = \sum_{i=1}^n A_i X_i$, A_i is any acoustical parameter.

Results and discussion

The following ternary liquid systems were taken up for study at 303, 308 and 313 K :

System I : chlorobenzene + 1-butanol + acetophenone

System II : bromobenzene + 1-butanol + acetophenone

System III : nitrobenzene + 1-butanol + acetophenone

The experimentally determined values of density (ρ), viscosity (η) and ultrasonic velocity (U) for the three liquid systems are tabulated in Table 1. The acoustical parameters such as adiabatic compressibility (β), intermolecular free length (L_f), free volume (V_f), internal pressure (π_i) for the above three liquid systems are furnished in Table 2. Similarly, the molar volume (V_m) and acoustic impedance (Z) for the three systems are given in Table 3. The evaluated excess values of adiabatic compressibility (β^E), excess free length (L_f^E), excess free volume (V_f^E), excess internal pressure (π_i^E) and excess molar volume (V_m^E) for all the three liquid systems are listed in Table 4.

It is observed from Table 1 that in all the three ternary liquid systems, the ρ and U increase with increasing concentrations of substituted benzenes, such as chlorobenzene, bromobenzene and nitrobenzene, whereas the values of η exhibit the decreasing trend. The variation of ultrasonic velocity in a mixture depends upon the increase (or) decrease of intermolecular free length after mixing the components. On the basis of a model for sound propagation proposed by Eyring and Kincaid¹², ultrasonic velocity should decrease, if the intermolecular free length increases and vice-versa. This is in fact observed in the present investigation for all the three liquid systems. It is evident that the values of the adiabatic compressibility

Table 1. The values of density (ρ), viscosity (η) and velocity (U) at 303, 308 and 313 K for Systems I, II and III

x_1	x_3	Density ρ (kg/m ³)			Viscosity η ($\times 10^{-3}$ Nsm ⁻²)			Velocity U (m/s)		
		303 K	308 K	313 K	303 K	308 K	313 K	303 K	308 K	313 K
System I : chlorobenzene + 1-butanol + acetophenone										
0.0000	0.6000	944.1	939.4	933.9	1.4332	1.3053	1.1989	1321.7	1315.2	1307.5
0.0997	0.4995	947.8	943.5	941.3	1.3568	1.2053	1.1609	1326.9	1320.9	1317.8
0.2002	0.3998	956.1	952.6	950.3	1.3257	1.2011	1.1391	1338.5	1328.3	1330.4
0.3000	0.3001	960.4	953.9	951.8	1.2257	1.1132	1.0133	1344.1	1333.5	1332.5
0.3924	0.1962	964.9	959.2	957.7	1.0678	0.9758	0.9024	1350.4	1342.3	1339.6
0.4999	0.0999	967.7	966.4	964.5	0.9935	0.9428	0.8298	1354.2	1352.4	1350.4
0.5968	0.0000	975.8	970.9	968.1	0.9259	0.8530	0.7925	1364.2	1358.5	1353.9
System II : bromobenzene + 1-butanol + acetophenone										
0.0000	0.6000	944.1	939.4	933.9	1.4332	1.3053	1.1989	1321.7	1315.2	1307.5
0.0999	0.5000	981.2	978.4	974.2	1.3591	1.2836	1.1863	1374.9	1368.9	1362.9
0.2000	0.3999	989.1	986.2	983.6	1.2717	1.1674	1.0728	1383.6	1381.2	1377.1
0.3000	0.2999	995.6	992.6	987.1	1.2048	1.1021	1.0174	1392.6	1388.2	1381.0
0.3405	0.2199	1001.0	998.0	995.3	1.0987	1.0205	0.9554	1400.7	1396.6	1392.7
0.5000	0.0998	1006.3	1003.5	1000.4	1.0332	0.9428	0.8732	1408.6	1404.3	1400.1
0.6000	0.0000	1011.7	1008.8	1005.9	0.9541	0.8773	0.8165	1416.6	1411.9	1407.7
System III : nitrobenzene + 1-butanol + acetophenone										
0.0000	0.5999	945.6	940.7	935.3	1.4358	1.3512	1.2274	1323.1	1317.6	1308.7
0.1001	0.4999	963.7	960.8	954.0	1.3892	1.3082	1.2110	1332.9	1330.2	1323.3
0.1640	0.4180	972.0	969.1	968.0	1.3713	1.2969	1.2047	1341.3	1336.0	1330.4
0.2999	0.3000	982.8	979.9	978.7	1.3528	1.2725	1.1983	1353.5	1348.2	1342.4
0.3999	0.2001	987.9	982.9	978.0	1.3342	1.2479	1.1649	1362.9	1356.9	1348.9
0.5000	0.0999	995.9	993.8	984.4	1.2992	1.2226	1.1488	1375.2	1371.3	1366.8
0.5999	0.0000	1001.9	996.2	992.6	1.2581	1.1621	1.0736	1382.7	1375.3	1368.9

(β) decrease with increasing concentrations of substituted benzenes in all the three liquid systems. In acetophenone, the carbonyl group is highly polar and hence has a high percentage of ionic character¹³. There is a negative charge on the carbonyl oxygen atom of acetophenone. Hence, one would expect a strong interactions with substituted benzenes. The decrease in adiabatic compressibility may be attributed to the internal interactions between π -electrons of C=O bond and π -electrons of the benzene ring¹⁴.

It is noticed that the L_f decreases with the increasing concentration of substituted benzenes in all the three liquid systems (Table 2). The acetophenone is a highly polar molecule ($\mu = 2.96$) and it may enhance the polarities of the substituted benzenes. The π -electron density in derivatives of benzene ring depends upon the group which is attached to it. The heteromolecular interaction between

component molecules necessarily depends upon the net electron density in the ring. As the electron-withdrawing nature of the group/atom increases, the intermolecular interaction is expected to increase. Hence, a decrease in free length (L_f) is noticed. Further, the decrease in L_f with increase in temperature as expected, due to thermal expansion of liquids, which are noticed from the Table 2. The values of V_f are found to be increased with increasing molar concentration of substituted benzenes in all the three liquid systems. The loss of dipolar association and difference in size and shape between the unlike molecules¹⁵ may lead to an increase in V_f . Further, the decreasing trend of internal pressure in all the three liquid systems clearly confirms this.

As, the 1-butanol, a primary alcohol and also a polar one, which is in association with acetophenone forms hydrogen bonding. According to Grace Selvarani *et al.*¹⁶,

Table 2. The values of adiabatic compressibility (β), free length (L_f), free volume (V_f) and internal pressure (π_i) at 303, 308 and 313 K

x_1	x_3	Adiabatic compressibility $\beta (\times 10^{-10} \text{ m}^2 \text{ N}^{-1})$			Free length $L_f (\times 10^{-10} \text{ m})$			Free volume $V_f (\times 10^{-7} \text{ m}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1})$			Internal pressure $\pi_i (\times 10^6 \text{ Nm}^{-2})$		
		303 K	308 K	313 K	303 K	308 K	313 K	303 K	308 K	313 K	303 K	308 K	313 K
System I : chlorobenzene + 1-butanol + acetophenone													
0.0000	0.6000	6.0623	6.1537	6.2619	0.4913	0.4989	0.5080	1.0265	1.1722	1.3201	474.94	464.00	453.91
0.0997	0.4996	5.9910	6.0733	6.1167	0.4884	0.4956	0.5021	1.1079	1.3143	1.3853	469.56	460.05	447.91
0.2003	0.3998	5.8379	5.9140	5.9448	0.4821	0.4924	0.4949	1.1496	1.3294	1.4302	465.86	452.55	445.63
0.3000	0.3001	5.7626	5.8771	5.9169	0.4789	0.4876	0.4938	1.2865	1.4668	1.6888	452.34	437.96	424.14
0.3924	0.1962	5.6826	5.7858	5.8117	0.4756	0.4838	0.4897	1.5538	1.7627	1.9761	430.34	418.26	408.76
0.4999	0.0999	5.6349	5.6572	5.6847	0.4736	0.4782	0.4840	1.7339	1.8718	2.2621	416.06	412.54	393.07
0.5968	0.0000	5.5534	5.5805	5.6351	0.4702	0.4751	0.4819	1.9312	2.4236	2.4112	405.83	395.40	387.21
System II : bromobenzene + 1-butanol + acetophenone													
0.0000	0.6000	6.0623	6.1483	6.2619	0.4913	0.4987	0.5080	1.0277	1.1721	1.3199	474.83	460.40	447.96
0.0999	0.5000	5.3912	5.4539	5.5259	0.4633	0.4697	0.4772	1.2437	1.3468	1.5054	446.40	441.12	430.65
0.2000	0.3999	5.2813	5.3150	5.3604	0.4585	0.4637	0.4700	1.4607	1.6565	1.8721	415.72	404.44	393.89
0.3000	0.2749	5.1787	5.2270	5.3117	0.4541	0.4598	0.4679	1.6814	1.9127	2.1396	389.69	378.67	367.09
0.3405	0.2199	5.1069	5.1366	5.1506	0.4509	0.4558	0.4607	2.0171	2.2437	2.4662	362.37	354.79	348.73
0.5000	0.0998	5.0075	5.0531	5.0991	0.4465	0.4521	0.4584	2.3681	2.7044	3.0200	335.69	325.83	318.50
0.6000	0.0000	4.9253	4.9719	5.0164	0.4428	0.4485	0.4547	2.4992	2.8532	3.5241	311.62	303.66	297.57
System III : nitrobenzene + 1-butanol + acetophenone													
0.0000	0.5999	6.0399	6.1583	6.2418	0.4904	0.4952	0.5072	1.0252	1.1159	1.2759	474.97	460.37	447.84
0.1001	0.4999	5.8401	5.8819	5.9857	0.4822	0.4878	0.4967	1.0939	1.1936	1.3297	470.49	463.34	452.33
0.1641	0.4180	5.7179	5.7806	5.8358	0.4771	0.4836	0.4904	1.1319	1.2234	1.3579	466.74	461.39	452.54
0.2999	0.3000	5.5534	5.6135	5.6697	0.4702	0.4765	0.4834	1.1751	1.2803	1.3921	463.67	457.15	451.41
0.3999	0.2001	5.4490	5.5252	5.6191	0.4652	0.4727	0.4812	1.2714	1.3369	1.4694	458.94	450.64	442.26
0.5001	0.0999	5.3089	5.3505	5.4021	0.4597	0.4652	0.4719	1.2897	1.4068	1.5369	451.76	445.47	438.67
0.5999	0.0000	5.2201	5.3065	5.3759	0.4559	0.4633	0.4707	1.3704	1.5312	1.7123	443.64	432.92	422.84

the molecular association is due to the hydroxyl group of 1-alkanol and acetophenone. According to them, aromatic ketones such as acetophenone are more associated with alcohols than the aliphatic one. Since alkanols are liquids¹⁰ which are associated through hydrogen bonding and in the pure state, they exhibit an equilibrium between multimer and monomer species. Further, when the substituted benzenes such as nitrobenzene is mixed with 1-butanol, the NO_2 group can interact with -OH group^{17,18}. The aromatic derivatives set up on interaction between the π -electrons cloud and the hydroxyl group. This interaction is of minor intensity compared with hydrogen bonding, but they may lead to formation of intermolecular complexes¹⁹.

The values of acoustic impedance (Z) (Table 3) is found to increase with concentration and decrease with

rise in temperature. When an acoustic wave travels in a medium, there is a variation of pressure from particle to particle. The ratio of the instantaneous pressure excess at any particle of the medium to the instantaneous velocity of that particle is known as 'specific acoustic impedance' of the medium. This factor is governed by the inertial and elastic properties of the medium. It is important to examine specific acoustic impedance in relation to concentration and temperature. When a plane ultrasonic wave is set up in a liquid, the pressure and hence density and refractive index show specific variations with distance from the source along the direction of propagation. Such an increasing values of acoustic impedance (Z) further support the possibility of molecular interactions between the unlike molecules. It is seen from the Table 3 that the molar volume (V_m) decreases with increasing con-

Table 3. The values of molar volume (V_m) and acoustic impedance (Z) at 303, 308 and 313 K for Systems I, II and III

x_1	x_3	Molar volume $V_m (\times 10^{-3} \text{ m}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1})$			Acoustic impedance $Z (\times 10^6 \text{ kg m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1})$		
		303 K	308 K	313 K	303 K	308 K	313 K
System I : chlorobenzene + 1-butanol + acetophenone							
0.0000	0.6000	0.1077	0.1083	0.1089	1.2479	1.2355	1.2212
0.0997	0.4996	0.1065	0.1071	0.1072	1.2577	1.2464	1.2405
0.2003	0.3998	0.1048	0.1052	0.1054	1.2797	1.2601	1.2583
0.3000	0.3001	0.1036	0.1043	0.1045	1.2910	1.2721	1.2683
0.3924	0.1962	0.1014	0.1020	0.1021	1.3030	1.2875	1.2831
0.4999	0.0999	0.1009	0.1010	0.1012	1.3104	1.3070	1.3026
0.5968	0.0000	0.0964	0.0966	0.0958	1.3312	1.3190	1.3107
System II : bromobenzene + 1-butanol + acetophenone							
0.0000	0.6000	0.1078	0.1083	0.1089	1.2479	1.2355	1.2212
0.0999	0.5000	0.1084	0.1097	0.1098	1.3491	1.3394	1.3278
0.2000	0.3999	0.1103	0.1106	0.1109	1.3685	1.3621	1.3546
0.3000	0.2799	0.1136	0.1142	0.1154	1.3865	1.3780	1.3631
0.3405	0.2197	0.1157	0.1163	0.1160	1.4021	1.3939	1.3862
0.5000	0.0998	0.1194	0.1197	0.1201	1.4176	1.4092	1.4006
0.6000	0.0000	0.1224	0.1227	0.1233	1.4332	1.4244	1.4160
System III : nitrobenzene + 1-butanol + acetophenone							
0.0000	0.5999	0.1076	0.1081	0.1088	1.2512	1.2395	1.2241
0.1001	0.4999	0.1062	0.1074	0.1079	1.2846	1.2781	1.2624
0.1641	0.4180	0.1059	0.1063	0.1062	1.3038	1.2948	1.2879
0.2999	0.3000	0.1044	0.1054	0.1051	1.3303	1.3212	1.3138
0.3999	0.2001	0.1042	0.1043	0.1049	1.3465	1.3338	1.3192
0.5001	0.0999	0.1036	0.1039	0.1041	1.3696	1.3629	1.3543
0.5999	0.0000	0.1033	0.1027	0.1033	1.3854	1.3701	1.3588

centration of substituted benzenes for Systems I and III, while it increases for System II and the same increases with rise of temperature. This may probably would be caused from the fact that thermal energy facilitates an increase in the molecular separation²⁰ in the liquid mixtures which lead to an increase in molar volume (V_m) with rise of temperature.

In order to understand the nature of molecular interactions between the components of the liquid mixtures, it is of interest to discuss the same in term of excess parameters rather than actual values. Non-ideal liquid mixtures show considerable deviation from linearity in their physical behaviour with respect to concentration and these have been interpreted as arising from the presence of strong or weak interactions. The extent of deviation depends upon the nature of the constituents and composi-

tion of the mixtures. The excess values of β^E , L_f^E , V_f^E , π_j^E and V_m^E for all the three liquid systems are furnished in Table 4. It is learnt that the dispersion forces are responsible for possessing positive excess values, while dipole-dipole, dipole-induced dipole, charge transfer interaction and hydrogen bonding between unlike molecules are responsible for possessing negative excess values²¹.

In the present study, the excess values of β^E and L_f^E , exhibit negative deviations in all the three liquid systems over the entire composition range (Table 4). The strength of interaction between the component molecules increase, when excess values tend to become increasingly negative. It may be interpreted due to dipole-induced dipole or dipole-dipole interactions between the unlike molecules. Further, the negative values of β^E in all the three liquid systems indicate the existence of strong

Table 4. The excess values of adiabatic compressibility (β^E), free length (L_f^E), free volume (V_f^E) and internal pressure (π_i^E) and molar volume (V_m^E) at 303, 308 and 313 K

x_1	x_3	Excess adiabatic compressibility			Excess free length			Excess free volume			Excess internal pressure			Excess molar volume		
		303 K	308 K	313 K	303 K	308 K	313 K	303 K	308 K	313 K	303 K	308 K	313 K	303 K	308 K	313 K
		System I : chlorobenzene + 1-butanol + acetophenone														
0.0000	0.6000	-0.0769	-0.0922	-0.1220	-0.0020	-0.0016	-0.0009	0.0666	0.0789	0.0884	-81	-74	-69	-0.0250	-0.0265	-0.0279
0.0997	0.4996	-0.2673	-0.2958	-0.3927	-0.0061	-0.007	-0.0104	0.0721	0.0865	0.097	-82	-73	-71	-0.0467	-0.0500	-0.0288
0.2003	0.3998	-0.5346	-0.4933	-0.6847	-0.0174	-0.015	-0.0229	0.1002	0.1162	0.1171	-80	-76	-68	-0.0134	-0.0686	-0.0459
0.3000	0.3001	-0.7260	-0.7300	-0.8347	-0.0257	-0.025	-0.0294	0.1270	0.1273	0.1296	-87	-86	-85	-0.0479	-0.0439	-0.0502
0.3924	0.1962	-0.7961	-0.8131	-0.9250	-0.0268	-0.038	-0.0352	0.1329	0.1783	0.1815	-94	-90	-87	-0.0991	-0.0955	-0.0984
0.4999	0.0999	-1.0873	-1.1915	-1.3128	-0.0411	-0.045	-0.0442	0.1352	0.1809	0.2198	-112	-101	-108	-0.0874	-0.0966	-0.1055
0.5968	0.0000	-1.2930	-1.3967	-1.4937	-0.0499	-0.054	-0.0503	0.1928	0.2037	0.2261	-120	-115	-111	-0.1194	-0.1201	-0.1253
		System II : bromobenzene + 1-butanol + acetophenone														
0.0000	0.6000	-0.0765	-0.0974	-0.1217	-0.0014	-0.0014	-0.0001	0.0675	0.0790	0.0884	-81	-77	-75	-0.0249	-0.0264	-0.0278
0.0999	0.5000	-0.8022	-0.8386	-0.8992	-0.0285	-0.0297	-0.0317	0.1728	0.1394	0.1360	-105	-93	-88	-0.0545	-0.0546	-0.0549
0.2000	0.3999	-0.9660	-1.0236	-1.1055	-0.0357	-0.0378	-0.0408	0.2789	0.3278	0.3713	-132	-125	-121	-0.0523	-0.0545	-0.0580
0.3000	0.2799	-1.1223	-1.1576	-1.1947	-0.0425	-0.0437	-0.0447	0.3888	0.4692	0.5041	-153	-146	-143	-0.0493	-0.0476	-0.0429
0.3405	0.2199	-1.3597	-1.4116	-1.5113	-0.0524	-0.0545	-0.0589	0.7230	0.7983	0.8038	-193	-183	-174	-0.0749	-0.0736	-0.0761
0.5000	0.0998	-1.4018	-1.4224	-1.6896	-0.0550	-0.0556	-0.0579	0.8543	1.0228	1.1157	-198	-191	-184	-0.0368	-0.0333	-0.0332
0.6000	0.0000	-1.5374	-1.5113	-1.7125	-0.0613	-0.0613	-0.0602	0.9956	1.0537	1.4850	-218	-209	-201	-0.0308	-0.0257	-0.0248
		System III : nitrobenzene + 1-butanol + acetophenone														
0.0000	0.5999	-0.0996	-0.0880	-0.1424	-0.0011	-0.0021	-0.0027	0.0649	0.0444	0.0227	-81	-78	-75	-0.0216	-0.0225	-0.0251
0.1001	0.4999	-0.2388	-0.3045	-0.3369	-0.0043	-0.0066	-0.0074	0.1514	0.1207	0.1202	-92	-80	-77	-0.0123	-0.0074	-0.0103
0.1641	0.4180	-0.3881	-0.4361	-0.5201	-0.0101	-0.0117	-0.0147	0.2205	0.1882	0.1849	-106	-93	-86	-0.0127	-0.0031	-0.0090
0.2999	0.3000	-0.4060	-0.4548	-0.5314	-0.0106	-0.0123	-0.0149	0.2685	0.2283	0.2669	-110	-101	-88	-0.0144	-0.0110	-0.0060
0.3999	0.2001	-0.4501	-0.4836	-0.5206	-0.0121	-0.0132	-0.0141	0.3284	0.3283	0.3220	-129	-110	-103	-0.0252	-0.0292	-0.0242
0.5001	0.0999	-0.5299	-0.5986	-0.6763	-0.0153	-0.0179	-0.0205	0.4185	0.4184	0.4128	-134	-121	-112	-0.0231	-0.0163	-0.0127
0.5999	0.0000	-0.5591	-0.5838	-0.6419	-0.0163	-0.017	-0.0188	0.6166	0.5570	0.5169	-148	-140	-134	-0.0175	-0.0324	-0.0318

interaction. A possible explanation may be that the oxygen atom of carbonyl group of acetophenone being strongly electronegative would act as a good electron acceptor towards the π -electrons of the aromatic ring thereby forming donor-acceptor complexes²². It is observed that negative deviations in β^E increases with concentrations as the strength of the molecular interaction between unlike molecules increases. It is observed that V_f^E values are tabulated in Table 4 exhibit negative values in all the three liquid systems over the entire range of composition clearly suggest the existence of specific interactions existing between the unlike molecules. The π_1^E which is described in terms of molecular interactions, whose negative values clearly support this.

The excess values of molar volume values are furnished in Table 4. According to Tiwari *et al.*²³, the excess values of V_m^E are influenced by

- (i) the loss of dipolar associations and differences in size and shape,
- (ii) dipole-dipole, dipole-induced dipole interactions or charge transfer complexation between the unlike molecules.

The former effect leads to expansion in volume and the latter contributes to contraction in volume. The actual V_m^E depends upon the balance between these two opposing considerations. The reason for acquiring the negative V_m^E may be interpreted as the formation of a hydrogen bond of type $X \cdots H-O$ ($X = Cl, Br$ and NO_2) between aromatic hydrocarbon and the alcohol and changes free volume, interstitial accommodation and conformation changes in acetophenone and aromatic hydrocarbons²⁴ in the aggregate of alkanol appear to occur in these mixtures. Also, the negative value of V_m^E is further attributed to the charge transfer between the π -electrons of aromatic molecules and the carbonyl group of acetophenone.

It is seen that the mixtures of acetophenone and 1-butanol with chlorobenzene and bromobenzene may be attributed to the existence of dipole-dipole interactions or dipole-induced dipole interactions between unlike molecules, as the aromatic nucleus of chlorobenzene and bromobenzene is activated by resonance effect. Though,

the dipole moments of chlorobenzene and bromobenzene are nearly similar, the ternary mixture which contains bromobenzene shows more excess negative values than with chlorobenzene. This may be accounted as better charge accommodation of bromine atom through its vacant d-orbitals. The experimental data in the present study suggest that the factors, which are favourable for latter effect, which account for the existence of dipole-dipole interactions present in the liquid mixtures. The negative values of V_m^E in all the three liquid systems clearly supporting this prediction. Hence, from the evaluated excess parameters it is obvious that strong interactions (dipole-dipole interaction) exist between the unlike molecules present in the components of the mixtures.

The some of the above excess properties were fitted to Redlich-Kister¹¹ polynomial equation,

$$Y^E = x_1 x_3 \sum_{i=1}^K A_i (x_1 - x_3)^i \quad (7)$$

where Y^E refers to excess properties, x_1 and x_3 are the mole fractions of the components of the ternary mixtures. The coefficients (A_i) were obtained by fitting equation to experimental values using least squares regression method. In each case, the optimal number of coefficients were ascertained from an approximation of the variation in the standard deviation (σ). The calculated values of coefficients a_0 , a_1 and a_2 values are along with the σ are listed in Table 5. The Redlich-Kister polynomials usually applied to test the validity of the excess values. The excess parameters evaluated on the basis of experimental findings such as density, viscosity, ultrasonic velocity etc. To test the deviation between ideal values of pure liquids and the corresponding experimental values, the Redlich-Kister polynomials are employed. Further, the coefficients a_0 , a_1 and a_2 , whose values lie in such a way that the values of σ becomes very meagre and small. In the case of non-accuracy of these coefficients, which will result in larger deviation in the values of σ .

The standard deviation σ was calculated using the equation,

$$\sigma^2 = \frac{1}{n-m} \left[Y_{\text{exp}}^E - Y_{\text{cal}}^E \right]^2 \quad (8)$$

where n is the number of data points and m is the number of coefficients.

Table 5. Redlich-Kister coefficients and standard deviation (σ) values

Parameters	System	Temp. (K)	a_0	a_1	a_2	σ
$\beta^E (\times 10^{-10} \text{ m}^2 \text{ N}^{-1})$	I	303	-16.6362	-13.6998	-1694.6400	0.6514
		308	-16.3869	-30.1346	-2039.7900	0.7039
		313	-21.4895	-95.6377	-2531.1300	0.7521
	II	303	-32.6699	-79.2649	-2267.4700	0.7746
		308	-34.3501	-88.0445	-2273.5900	0.7628
		313	-36.7554	-104.9710	-2446.2500	0.8158
	III	303	-12.5453	-66.3353	-1061.7700	0.2847
		308	-14.7028	-105.8910	-1382.8500	0.2954
		313	-17.2018	-138.5710	-1650.0100	0.3297
$L_f^E (\times 10^{-10} \text{ m})$	I	303	-0.5325	-1.4087	-72.1869	0.0254
		308	-0.5029	-2.3690	-88.2368	0.0274
		313	-0.6823	-2.4188	-62.8260	0.0253
	II	303	-1.1919	-1.8696	-83.3226	0.0307
		308	-1.2505	-2.0243	-83.3798	0.0308
		313	-1.3324	-2.2817	-87.4727	0.0041
	III	303	-0.2979	-1.0037	-27.0387	0.0083
		308	-0.3725	-2.4539	-39.1551	0.0086
		313	-0.4565	-3.6794	-48.8154	0.0096
$V_f^E (\times 10^{-7} \text{ m}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1})$	I	303	4.3583	27.9694	294.8410	0.1032
		308	3.7001	3.8298	272.3440	0.1096
		313	4.0565	22.0143	461.9610	0.1216
	II	303	8.3038	-72.0795	1089.1100	0.5020
		308	8.9946	-86.4550	1319.6500	0.5302
		313	9.9191	-61.3426	1638.1000	0.7451
	III	303	7.5342	26.8390	772.1780	0.3100
		308	6.1897	8.1772	713.0420	0.2795
		313	6.4581	-0.3031	618.4030	0.2589

Conclusion :

It is very obvious that there exists a strong interactions existing among the unlike molecules. Such a strong molecular interaction exists between acetophenone and substituted benzenes through dipole-dipole interactions and the molecular association between acetophenone and 1-butanol is through hydrogen bonding. The formation of donor-acceptor complexes were also observed in the present investigation.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Dr. AN Kannappan, Professor and Head, Department of Physics, Annamalai University for his encouragement.

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